

Jungle Ruins and Sacred Forests: Ecologies of the Forgotten Monument

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The study of sacred monuments is related to questions of ecology, as non-human forces: vegetal growth, elemental decay, spectral inhabitation, produce and transform the meaning of built sites across time. Communities, artists, and postcolonial states often negotiate the life and death of monuments through processes that transcend conservationist frameworks. Ecological time is also a medium of power, shaping whose heritage is preserved, whose is erased, and whose is left to the forest. An example is the Boo Da shrine complex of northeast Thailand, where older wooden structures are deliberately allowed to decay beside their concrete replacements: neither discarded nor formally conserved, but tended in a register that Western museum practice struggles to name. At the same time, concepts and practices of ‘ruination’ are culturally and epochally specific. As a result, multi- and transdisciplinary approaches to the ‘forgotten monument’ are scarce; juxtaposing and integrating cross-disciplinary, cross-regional, and cross-temporal perspectives can contribute significantly to our understanding of ecological agency and heritage. The session studied and discussed which aspects of ecological process shape sacred sites, and how sacred sites, in turn, shape the communities and non-human agents that inhabit them. While convened by a researcher of Buddhist manuscript traditions and sacred geographies of the Pāla period in eastern India, the participants of this session study ruination, conservation, and memory from medieval Thailand to colonial Mexico to contemporary Singapore, focusing on case studies in Asia, South Asia, Southeast Asia, and the Americas in disciplines within art history, curatorial studies, film studies, and postcolonial studies. This wide range of perspectives created an interdisciplinary platform for discussion on ecology, materiality, and the ontological transformation of monuments.

The central aim of the session was to investigate the reciprocal relation between ecological process(es) and the sacred monument. As an interdisciplinary session, various kinds of sites and media were presented: ancestral shrines, photographic archives, curatorial collaborations with living artists, horror-comedy films, and Sufi dargahs. Multiple papers also explored the agency of non-human actors: spirits, forests, mangroves, *djinns*, as authors of the monument’s ongoing transformation. ALISA SANTIKARN (Vienna) focused on the Boo Da

spirit shrines of northeast Thailand, drawing on fieldwork across thirteen sites and participation in a cleansing ritual in April 2025. She introduced the concept of ‘curated decay’, drawn from Caitlin DeSilvey, to describe the practice of allowing wooden shrines to deteriorate naturally beside their concrete replacements: too sacred to discard, left for nature while offerings continue to be made. The question of what counts as care, and for whom conservation is practised, was central to several papers: DAISY SILVER (UCL / Northridge) reconstructed the photographic practice of Armando Salas Portugal through his less-examined documentation of Mesoamerican ruins and volcanic terrain, arguing that the encroaching jungle at Bonampak and the lava fields of El Pedregal position nature as a force in shaping Mexican modernity. Conversely, JOELLA KIU (Singapore Art Museum) focused on the curatorial dimensions of ecological listening. Working alongside artist ila on the long-term project *Instrumental Plot*, she argued that meaningful engagement with mangrove environments requires ‘deep listening’: a receptivity to being affected by forces beyond human control, and that the artist-curator collaboration must be dialogic rather than transactional. SOUMYA VATS (Ashoka) discussed the spatial politics of ruins and forests in contemporary Hindi horror-comedy, showing how the Maddock Films cycle deploys heterotopic landscapes as repositories of suppressed oral histories. NARMEEN SAJID (Independent) studied the Sufi shrines of Khuldabad in western India, arguing that the *djinn*s who haunt neglected monuments figure the persistence of memory, and that physical decay marks transitions in social identity rather than endpoints.

The presence of non-human agency was shown in two distinct ways. First, ecological forces operate as co-authors of the monument. Santikarn proposed the Jum, the shrine caretaker who communicates with the Boo Da spirit, as an analogy for the curator-conservator, responsible for both material and immaterial care. Silver argued that ecological imagination, rather than nationalist ideology alone, was the more fundamental force shaping Salas Portugal’s visual construction of Mexican modernism: vines and lava seem to pre-author the modernist house. Second, in many of the presented cases, the boundary between the animate and inanimate was under negotiation. Kiu’s fieldwork in Bintan placed thriving mangrove systems alongside the destruction caused by bauxite mining, and the artworks produce, including ila’s forthcoming *mantera apotropaic*, conceived as both invocation and alternative cartography: map mangrove ecosystems through ecological, cultural, and spiritual dimensions simultaneously, drawing on regional beliefs that imbue mangroves with sentience.

The ‘forgotten monument’, however, is not a temporal category that can be studied in itself, as it consists of imaginations of absence that are always politically produced. The present condition of neglect and the past of inhabitation are therefore inherently intertwined. For example, the *djinns* haunting the Khuldabad shrines, as Sajid showed, mark what structural neglect has attempted to erase. Yet on the other hand, she argued, the afterlives of these sites extend through the renegotiation of their relationships to the sacred and the profane, exposing both the violence of erasure and the resistance of communities. Third, ecology is an instrument of power. Vats showed that the jungle and the ruin are the central spatial figures of the Maddock horror-comedy cycle, functioning as sites where suppressed cultural memory resurfaces through popular genre, but also where progressive impulses are contained within commercially palatable conventions. Colonial power also impacted the photographic imagination of the modern, as Silver demonstrated: Salas Portugal’s ecological sensibility was shaped by post-revolutionary debates on land, memory, and inheritance that cannot be separated from the colonial history of those landscapes. JOELLA KIU (Singapore) analysed the intersection of ecological and archival loss in ila’s *Animacies of Absence*, which approaches loss as obscured presence rather than disappearance. The interaction with a colonial past as a condition of present artistic production was a thread that connected Kiu’s, Silver’s, and Vats’s papers: all three showed how the legacies of colonial landscape regimes continue to shape how forests, ruins, and sacred sites are seen, valued, and narrated.

On all three panels of the session, discussion was included in the programme to strengthen future interdisciplinary work. The Q&A centred on two principal themes. The first was the question of artists’ relationships to communities, particularly in the context of Kiu’s paper: how does the artist, and the curator working alongside the artist, navigate the difference between belonging to an environment and speaking on its behalf, and what institutional conditions make genuine openness to ecological time possible? The second thread drew together Santikarn’s concept of ‘curated decay’ and the broader session argument about non-human agency, asking where care ends and abandonment begins, and whether the distinction itself is always meaningful across the cultural contexts the session addressed. Just as during the general discussion, the question of vocabulary proved intellectually stimulating: ‘ruination’ in art history, ‘hauntology’ in postcolonial studies, ‘deep listening’ in curatorial practice, and ‘curated decay’ in conservation theory all name aspects of a shared phenomenon from different disciplinary angles.

Session overview:

Archishman Sarker (Ashoka University): Welcome and framing remarks

Paper 1: Alisa Santikarn (University of Vienna): ‘Rotten Wood, Concrete Shrine, Sacred Forest: Preserving the Boo Da Spirit in Northeast Thailand’

Paper 2: Daisy Silver (University College London / California State University, Northridge): ‘An Intricate Vegetal Embroidery: Armando Salas Portugal and Modern Mexican Ruins’

Paper 3: Joella Kiu (Singapore Art Museum): ‘Brackish Shrubbery: Deep Listening in the Mangroves’

Paper 4: Soumya Vats (Ashoka University): ‘From Abandonment to Popular(ity): Jungles and Ruins in Maddock Horror Film’

Paper 5: Narmeen Sajid (Independent Researcher): ‘Sacred Ecologies and the Horror of Neglect: Urbanisation and the Afterlives of Sufi Shrines in Khuldabad’

Discussion and closing remarks